

End Group of Polymethyl Methacrylate Obtained by Initiation with Permanganate Organic Acid Medox Pair

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Organic acids, viz. formic, acetic, propionic, butyric, lactic, oxalic, succinic, adipic, citric and tartaric acids were used as activators in combination with potassium permanganate as oxidant in presence of methylmethacrylate as monomer both in aqueous and non-aqueous media. While there was no polymerization with acetic, propionic, butyric, succinic and adipic acids, use of oxalic, lactic, citric and tartaric acids result in polymerization. The nature of endgroups present in such polymers have been studied and it was found that initiator fragments (from the organic acid) are incorporated at polymer chain ends. Carboxyl endgroups are incorporated in the polymers and where the acid used is hydroxy acid, hydroxyl group in polymers is also traced. The nature of endgroups and their extent of incorporation have been mostly dependent on the nature of the acid used.

It has been reported^{1,2} earlier that some reducing organic acids such as formic, oxalic, citric, tartaric and lactic acids initiate aqueous polymerization of methylmethacrylate in presence of light but they fail to do so in the dark. However, in conjunction with suitable oxidising agents they form good redox initiators, a very efficient one being permanganate-oxalic acid³. The present paper reports the results of our investigations on the use of various organic acids with permanganate as oxidant for polymerization of methylmethacrylate both in aqueous and non-aqueous media with special emphasis on identification and determination of end groups in the polymers.

Experimental

Material: Methylmethacrylate monomer was used for all polymerization experiments. It was purified by standard procedure⁴ before use. The carboxylic acids used as reductants and potassium permanganate as oxidant were all of analar grade (B.D.H). Dimethyl formamide (DMF) and ethylene carbonate (EC) were freshly distilled before use.

Preparation and Purification of Polymer: All polymerization experiments were done in nitrogen atmosphere at room temperature. In aqueous media the polymers were obtained in a precipitated phase, which was filtered, washed thoroughly and then dried in a vacuum oven at 40°-45°.

Non-aqueous solution polymerization was carried out in DMF and EC solution using potassium permanganate and oxalic acid as initiators in tubes sealed under vacuum.

The polymers obtained in solution were precipitated with methanol-petroleum ether mixtures. The polymers were then carefully purified by the method of repeated precipitation⁴.

Detection and Estimation of Endgroups: The purified polymers were then tested for carboxyl and hydroxyl endgroups which might have been incorporated during initiation of polymerization by the application of dye interaction⁵ and dye partition technique⁶ respectively developed in our laboratory. Quantitative determination of endgroups was carried out spectrophotometrically^{4,7,8}. The accuracy of endgroup determination by dye techniques lies in the range $\pm 10-15\%$.

Results and Discussions

Polymerization in Aqueous Media: The organic acids, viz., formic, acetic, propionic, butyric, lactic, oxalic, succinic, adipic, citric and tartaric acids were used as activators in combination with potassium permanganate as the oxidant in presence of methyl methacrylate as monomer in aqueous media.

On addition of permanganate in an aqueous solution of organic acid and methylmethacrylate, two types of experimental observations were made. With one group of organic acids there was no polymerization while with other group of acids, ready polymerization occurred. Acetic, propionic, butyric, succinic and adipic acids belong to the former group. In the case of these acids with permanganate as oxidant, the aqueous medium containing MMA became brownish black due to immediate separation of colloidal manganese dioxide which finally precipitated out and there was no polymerization of MMA. It was not ascertained whether there was any oxidation of the monomer in this case. It is very likely that oxidation of the monomer will take place. However, because permanganate concentrations are very low (vide Tables), it is difficult to analyse the extent of oxidation of the monomer which is present to the extent of about 0.1M in aqueous systems. On the other hand, no precipitation of MnO₂ occurred with the other group of organic acids, viz., oxalic, lactic², citric and tartaric acid but a cherry-red

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colored solution was first produced which slowly turned to a colorless solution. Polymerization started almost immediately or after a short induction period (sometimes after the discharge of the cherry-red colour) when the solution turned milky and produced polymers in very high yield. The polymer was separated from the aqueous phase by filtration and purified by precipitation (3-4 times) from benzene solution into a mixture of methanol and petroleum ether.

Endgroup Studies: Permanganate-Oxalic acid Systems: The results of endgroup analysis of polymethylmethacrylate obtained by initiation with permanganate-oxalic acid redox systems are presented in table 1. It is observed that carboxyl endgroups are present in all these polymers. This provides a direct evidence for the generation of carboxyl radicals in the present system. It is apparent from the results in Table 1 that a higher concentration of permanganate gave a more intense test for carboxyl endgroup and produced a polymer of low molecular weight. Quantitatively, an average of 1 to 1.3 carboxyl endgroups is found to be incorporated per polymer chain. Hydroxyl endgroups are not generally found in these polymers.

in these polymers has been verified by adopting both the procedures.

The mechanism of oxidation of oxalic acid by permanganate has been discussed by Launer and Yost¹⁰ and also by Basset and Sanderson¹¹. Intermediate formation of oxalate or carboxyl radical has been suggested.

The experimental demonstration of carboxyl endgroups provides a direct evidence for the formation of carboxyl radicals ($\overset{\cdot}{\text{C}}_2\text{O}_4$ or $\overset{\cdot}{\text{C}}\text{OO}^-$).

According to the results of polymerization kinetics reported by Palit and Konar¹², the termination of aqueous polymerization of MMA initiated by the present system appears to be bimolecular, the initiator exponent being of the order of 0.5. The total endgroup content as determined by dye techniques appears to be mostly one carboxyl per polymer chain. It appears therefore, that the termination in the present case occurs mainly by disproportionation.

Permanganate other Organic acid System: The results of endgroup analysis of polymethyl methacrylate initiated by permanganate-lactic acid, permanganate-tartaric acid and permanganate-citric acid are reported in table 2. Both carboxyl and hydroxyl groups are found to be present in these polymers. It appears therefore that the redox reaction between permanganate and all the above mentioned acids

TABLE 1—ENDGROUP ANALYSIS OF POLYMETHYLMETHACRYLATE INITIATED BY PERMANGANATE-OXALIC ACID REDOX IN AQUEOUS SYSTEM

Systems : MMA = 0.094 mole/l; Temp : 30°C;
Dark, N₂ atmosphere.

Catalyst Concentration		[η] dl/g	Endgroups per chain	
Permanganate × 10 ⁴ mole/l	Oxalic acid × 10 ³ mole/l		Carboxyl	Hydroxyl
3.16	7.93	0.44	0.93	0.03
5.00	7.93	0.28	1.12	nil
6.32	7.93	0.19	1.19	nil
6.32	11.87	0.30	1.32	nil
6.32	15.86	0.32	1.21	nil
10.00	5.00	0.25	1.06	0.04
20.00	5.00	0.18	1.12	nil
20.00	10.00	0.16	1.06	nil

In this connection, we would like to mention that our previous report⁹ of the presence of OH endgroup for the present system is not correct. We have now traced it to a defect in our experimental procedure followed therein. We then followed the phthalation technique whereby hydroxyl endgroups were converted to ionic carboxyl endgroups by reacting the polymer with phthalic anhydride. We have now found that excess phthalic anhydride if present even in traces (< 10⁻⁵M) would give response to the sensitive dye interaction test, and this was the source of error in our previous work. Only very stringent purification procedure will help to find out the correct picture of endgroup by adopting this procedure. In the present work, this pit fall has been avoided by converting -OH endgroup, if present, to sulfate group by treating the polymer with chlorosulfonic acid where excess chlorosulfonic acid can be removed more easily. The absence of OH endgroup

TABLE 2—ENDGROUP ANALYSIS OF POLYMETHYLMETHACRYLATE INITIATED BY PERMANGANATE WITH LACTIC ACID, TARTARIC ACID AND CITRIC ACID SEPARATELY IN AQUEOUS MEDIA

Systems : MMA = 0.094 mole/l; Temp : 30°C;
Dark, N₂ Atmosphere

Catalyst Concentration		[η] dl/g	Endgroups per chain		Total
Oxidant × 10 ⁴ mole/l	Acetivator × 10 ³ mole/l		Carboxyl	Hydroxyl	
Permanganate	Lactic acid				
	3.16	13.33	0.83	0.69	1.03
	5.04	13.33	0.61	0.75	1.05
	3.16	6.66	0.80	1.01	1.25
3.16	26.66	0.95	1.11	1.31	
Permanganate	Tartaric acid				
	3.16	6.66	0.78	1.20	2.23
	5.04	6.66	0.70	1.54	2.08
6.32	6.66	0.53	1.88	1.98	
Permanganate	Citric acid				
	3.16	5.20	1.60	2.17	3.05
	5.04	5.20	1.28	2.46	2.96
6.32	5.20	1.20	2.67	2.85	

proceeds through the intermediacy of both hydroxyl and carboxyl radicals or hydroxy-carboxylic radicals.

It is known that lactic acid is oxidised by permanganate producing acetaldehyde, pyruvic acid, formic acid as intermediate products. The following reaction scheme may be put forward to explain the experimental facts :

Quantitatively, it is observed that the carboxyl endgroups to the extent of 0.6–1.1 per chain and hydroxyl endgroup to the extent of 0.2–0.45 per chain are incorporated in the polymers. Therefore, it appears that the initiating radicals are either carboxyl bearing or hydroxyl bearing ones and the carboxyl ones take more active part in inducing polymerization and hence more predominantly incorporated in the polymers.

In permanganate-tartaric acid systems, the carboxyl endgroup content varies from 1.2–2.0 per chain and hydroxyl group content from 1.0 to 0.1 endgroup, the total being about two endgroups per chain. It is very difficult to ascertain the exact mechanism of generation of initiating radicals and the structure of the species only from endgroup estimation. It is known that tartaric acid on oxidation gives rise to tartronic acid, a hydroxy malonic acid which on further oxidation gives rise to formic acid and carbon dioxide. The endgroup analysis at least indicates the formation of a radical containing two carboxyl groups as evidenced by the presence of two carboxyl

endgroups in some of the polymers. Similarly, in permanganate-citric acid systems, about 2.0–2.6 carboxylic endgroup per chain and about 0.2–0.9 hydroxylic endgroup per chain (total being roughly about three endgroups per chain) are present in the polymer molecules. The oxidation of citric acid is known to give rise to keto-dicarboxylic acid which under drastic oxidation is ultimately transformed into acetone and carbon dioxide. It is very difficult to propose a reaction scheme for generation of intermediate radicals in this system also but from the existing knowledge of oxidation of citric acid and from the results of endgroup analysis it appears that polycarboxylic radicals are generated in solution, in the present system.

Polymerization in Non-aqueous Media : Ethylene carbonate (EC) and dimethyl formamide (DMF) are two solvents chosen as the media for non aqueous polymerization of methylmethacrylate using permanganate with oxalic acid and citric acid separately. No polymerization was found to occur either with permanganate alone or permanganate with (acetic, propionic, butyric, succinic and adipic) acid in these non-aqueous systems, a behaviour similar to that in aqueous media. In case of oxalic and citric acid system, the yield of polymer was about 15–30% in DMF solution and 10–15% in EC solution after four hours depending on the concentration of permanganate. Other systems such as permanganate with tartaric and lactic acid give rise to polymer in non-aqueous media but detailed study of endgroup was not undertaken.

Carboxylic endgroups are found to be present in all these polymers obtained by permanganate-oxalic acid system in EC and DMF media (Table 3). The results are almost similar to that in aqueous media. The interesting point is to note that the carboxyl group content in EC solvent is nearly one per chain and that in polymers obtained in presence of DMF

TABLE 3—ENDGROUP ANALYSIS OF POLYMETHYLMETHACRYLATE INITIATED BY PERMANGANATE-OXALIC ACID AND PERMANGANATE-CITRIC ACID IN NON-AQUEOUS MEDIA

System : MMA = 2 ml; Solvent : 2 ml; Dark; Temp : 35° ± 0.2° vac. sealed

Catalyst concentration		solvent used	[η] dl/g	Endgroups per chain		Total
Oxidant × 10 ⁴ mole/l	Activator × 10 ³ mole/l			Carboxyl	Hydroxyl	
Perman-ganate	Oxalic acid	Ethylene carbonate ⁺				
3.16	7.93	„	2.92	0.92	nil	0.92
4.74	7.93	„	2.80	0.95	nil	0.95
6.32	7.93	„	2.65	1.01	nil	1.01
3.16	7.93	DMF	2.74	0.68	nil	0.68
6.32	7.93	„	0.86	0.87	nil	0.87
6.32	15.86	„	1.96	0.84	nil	0.84
Perman-ganate	Citric acid	Ethylene ⁺ carbonate				
3.16	5.20	„	2.60	2.04	1.13	3.17
5.04	5.20	„	2.28	2.33	0.91	3.29
6.32	5.20	„	1.96	2.45	0.82	3.27

[S]/[M] = 1.57

[S]/[M] = 1.30

solvent is less, the polymers being obtained in both the cases under otherwise more or less comparable conditions. The molecular weight of the former is found to be higher than that of the latter as observed from $[\eta]$ values under comparable conditions. This clearly signifies that the chain transfer with DMF solvent occurs more frequently than that with EC solvent. Thus in DMF medium, the degree of incorporation of primary carboxyl radical is reduced. That the chain transfer with DMF solvent compared to that with ethylene carbonate is higher, has also been reported by Thomas *et al.*¹³ with polyacrylonitrile radical by determining their respective transfer constants.

Alike aqueous media both carboxylic and hydroxylic endgroups are found to be present in polymers initiated by permanganate citric acid in ethylene carbonate. The quantitative analysis reveals the presence of two carboxyl and one hydroxyl endgroup, the total being three per chain. The only significant difference between aqueous and non-aqueous systems for the present investigation lies in high values in the latter system.

Conclusion

It has been found that with KMnO_4^- organic acid systems as thermal redox initiators polymerization, occurs polymerization with formic, oxalic and hydroxy acids. Several other unsubstituted mono or dibasic acids were found to be ineffective. Initiator fragments (from the organic acid component) are incorporated at polymer chain ends. Carboxyl endgroups are

incorporated in all the polymers. Where the acid used is hydroxy acid, incorporation of hydroxyl groups in the polymers is also traced. The nature of the endgroups and their extent of incorporation have been found to be largely dependent on the nature of the acid used.

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